

FORMATION OF MORAL AND VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF ADOLESCENTS BY MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article deals with the relevance of the problem of the formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. Efficient ways of moral and volitional qualities formation during the introduction of physical education means have been worked out.

Key words: volitional qualities, moral qualities, physical education, means, teenagers.

Introduction. At all times, people highly valued such human qualities as morality, morality, will, character [1]. The deep socio-economic transformations taking place in modern society make us talk about the future of youth. At present, the moral guidelines are crumpled, the younger generation can be blamed for lack of spirituality, unbelief, and aggressiveness [2, 3].

The relevance of the problem of physical education of schoolchildren is in the first place today, along with the educational process. Physical education is an integral part of general culture, a sphere of social activity, which is a set of spiritual and material values created and used by society for the purpose of physical development of a person, strengthening his health, will and improving his motor activity [4, 5, 6].

Adolescence is the most difficult and complex of all childhood ages, which is a period of personality formation, at the same time it is the most crucial period [7, 8]. In adolescence, the foundations of morality are laid, social attitudes are formed,

attitudes towards oneself, towards people, towards society, in addition, character traits and the main forms of interpersonal behavior are stabilized at this age [9]. The problem is due to the fact that some of the secondary school graduates are poorly formed such important personal qualities as initiative, endurance, independence, courage, perseverance, discipline, collectivism [10, 11, 12, 13].

In general, physical education and sports have a general preventive effect on the human body, increase the level of his health [14]. A variety of physical exercises not only improve the physical training of students, but also educate the emotional-volitional sphere [15, 16]. Therefore, physical education and sports are a necessary condition for the development of a child's personality [17].

One of the more effective ways of moral-volitional qualities formation is the introduction of physical education means [18, 19, 20]. This conclusion can be reached as a result of observing problems among adolescents:

- poor physical development of adolescents;
- lack of interest in regular exercise;
- lack of physical and psychological endurance in young men;
- the absence of a cult of a healthy lifestyle.

The use of a complex of physical exercises solves the following tasks:

- preservation and strengthening of the physical health of schoolchildren;
- development of the need for regular physical education and sports, taking into account the specifics of the region;
- the formation in adolescents of the necessary personal qualities, self-esteem, endurance, confidence, self-control;
- assistance in the education of moral and volitional qualities, the further development of mental processes and teaching the basics of mental regulation;
- development of a personal idea of the values of a healthy lifestyle, the prestige of a high level of health as a condition for improving the emotional and volitional sphere of students.

At the end of the implementation of the physical education program, adolescents master the basics of relationships between people, the rules of cultural behavior and communication, the knowledge and skills of taking care of themselves and others, children are instilled with a sense of love for the Motherland, beauty, respect for the older generation, desire and ability to help those in need people [21, 22]. The inclusion of students in physical activities is also one of the main ways of becoming an active citizen. As already mentioned, will is only a generalized concept, behind which many different psychological phenomena are hidden. This is the conscious control of one's actions, and volitional effort, and its specific manifestations (volitional qualities). It is necessary to develop not an abstract will and not even an abstract "willpower", but specific components of the will and specific manifestations of "willpower" (volitional qualities), moreover, using methods specific to them [23, 24, 25].

A fairly common way among modern teenagers to develop volitional qualities of a personality is to engage in sports associated with great physical exertion and risk, such as requiring extraordinary strength and courage. These are boxing, karate, wrestling, weightlifting and other contact sports. Being carried away by many types of sports activities, first for the sake of developing strong-willed personal qualities, some teenagers then continue to engage in them to achieve high results. Thanks to this, the motivation to achieve success is further developed.

The desire to develop useful personality traits characteristic of adults of the same sex with them is characteristic not only of teenage boys, but also of teenage girls. However, unlike boys, the development of specific personality traits, similar to strong-willed ones, in girls is directed along a different path. For them, such activities in which the corresponding qualities are formed and consolidated are most often teachings, various types of arts, housekeeping, and women's sports.

Adolescent girls especially struggle to excel academically, with many taking up school subjects where they fail. The described gender and age differences

between boys and girls contribute to the fact that they develop perseverance and efficiency in precisely such types of activities that they will have to do as adults. All these features take into account physical education in the development of the student's personality.

Conclusions. Having instilled a love for physical education in adolescents, the confidence that they will engage in it in their later adult life increases dramatically. The powerful health-improving potential of physical education and sports allows the formation of moral and volitional qualities in adolescents and a harmoniously developed personality in each of them. A variety of physical exercises not only improve the physical condition of adolescents, but also educate the emotional and volitional sphere. Therefore, the combination of physical activity with the psycho-emotional development of the personality is a necessary condition for teaching physical education at the present stage.

References:

1. Turdimurodov D.Y. Pedagogical factors of external stimulation affecting the volitional efforts of schoolchildren during physical exercises of a different nature / D.Y. Turdimurodov // *Innovations in pedagogy and psychology*. - 2020. - №. 9. Issue 3. - P. 21-25.
2. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2022). Education and development of volitive qualities in schoolchildren by means of physical education. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(01), 59–62.
3. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2021). Спорт ўйинлари билан шуғулланиш жараёнида ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларнинг шаклланиш хусусиятлари. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, 3(9 (77)), 140-144.
4. Турдимуродов Д. Ю. (2020). Готовность подростков к волевым напряжениям и педагогические условия ее формирования в процессе физического воспитания в общеобразовательной школе. *Science, Research, Development*, 2, 309-311.

5. Йулдашевич, Т. Д. (2022). Воспитание и развитие волевых качеств у школьников средствами физического воспитания. *Ижтимоий фанларда инновация онлайн илмий журнали*, 2(1), 204–207.

6. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current Research Journal of Pedagogics (2767-3278)*, 2(09), 47-51.

7. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.

8. Турдимуродов, Д. (2021). Formation and education of will in schoolchildren in the process of physical education lesson. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(02), 64-74.

9. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Педагогические факторы внешней стимуляции влияющие на волевые усилия школьников при физических упражнениях разного характера. *Педагогика ва психологияда инновациялар*, 9(3).

10. Turdimurodov D.Y. Pedagogical factors of external stimulation affecting the volitional efforts of schoolchildren during physical exercises of a different nature / D.Y. Turdimurodov // *Innovations in pedagogy and psychology*. - 2020. - №. 9. Issue 3. - P. 21-25.

11. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2021). Особенности проявления волевых усилий в процессе внешней стимуляции у школьников 10-12 лет. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 1348-1354.

12. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2021). Ўқувчиларнинг иродавий сифатларини шакллантиришда жисмоний тарбия воситаларининг имкониятлари. *Инновации в педагогике и психологии*, 4(7).

13. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldoshevich. (2021). The formation of readiness for skilled tensions in the process of physical education. *Archive of Conferences*, 21-24.

14. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Willed qualities of a personality and ways of their formation in sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 12 (104), 689-692.

15. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Влияние занятий единоборствами на уровень проявления морально - волевых качеств учащихся общеобразовательной школы. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 691-698.

16. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Application of Innovative Technologies in the Process of Formation of Will Qualities. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 826–828.

17. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Peculiarities of Formation of Schoolchildren's Will Qualities in the Process of Sports Games. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 823-825.

18. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире Учредители: Общественная организация" Институт социальной трансформации"*, 140-144.

19. Турдимуродов Д. Й. Возможности средств физического воспитания в формировании волевых качеств у школьников / Д. Й. Турдимуродов. // *Инновации в педагогике и психологии*. -2021. - № 7. Выпуск 4. - С. 74-80

20. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Features of the manifestation of volitional efforts in the process of external stimulation in schoolchildren of 10-12 years old. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 1348-1354.

21. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Innovative technologies in the process of formation of will qualities. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 95–98.

22. Turdimuradov Dilmurad Yuldashevich. (2022). Self-education of volitional qualities in children of senior school age. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(06), 34–39.

23. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Жамият ва инновациялар*, 3(6/S), 74–80.

24. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2022). Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. *Problems and scientific solutions, Australia, Melbourne*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6933851>

25. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Урок физического воспитания как средство развития волевых качеств у школьников. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 74–80.